

SOCIOECONOMIC DRIVERS OF PREVENTIVE RISK MANAGEMENT AND RESILIENCE IN MAIZE–CASSAVA INTERCROPPING SYSTEMS IN KWARA STATE, NIGERIA

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<https://doi.org/10.70118/ajaas.032606010.09>

ABSTRACT

Small-scale farmers in Kwara State, Nigeria continue to face considerable production risks, and the extent to which socioeconomic drivers and preventive risk management strategies shape their resilience in maize–cassava inter-cropping systems remains insufficiently understood. This study examined socioeconomic drivers of preventive risk management and resilience in maize-cassava intercropping systems in Kwara State, Nigeria. Primary data were collected from 110 maize-cassava farmers through a multi-stage sampling technique and structured questionnaire. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze socioeconomic characteristics, identify the sources of production risks, and the preventive management strategies adopted by maize-cassava, while the Multivariate Probit model estimated the factors influencing the preventive management strategies of maize-cassava small-scale farmers in the study area. The Multivariate Probit results reveal a significant positive relationship among adaptation strategies that farming experience was significant at ($p \leq 0.01$), education level at ($p \leq 0.10$) and off-farm income at ($p \leq 0.01$). The findings suggest that farmers enhance their adaptive capacity by combining multiple strategies rather than relying on single practices. However, limited institutional and economic resources constrain optimal risk responses. The study concluded that building agricultural resilience requires integrated policy approaches that enhance farmers' knowledge, income diversification, and access to supportive services. Strengthening these factors will improve sustainable risk management and long-term agricultural productivity under climate variability.

Keywords: Resilience, Preventive Risk Management, Socioeconomic Drivers, Maize–Cassava Inter-cropping, and Small-Scale Farmers.

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture remains a cornerstone of Nigeria's economy, employing about 34% of the labor force and contributing roughly 23–25% to the nation's GDP (ILOSTAT, 2023; National Bureau of Statistics [NBS], 2025). The sector, which provides livelihood for millions of rural households, is dominated by smallholder farmers, who are responsible for a large chunk of the nation's food supply (Chiaka et al., 2022). Notwithstanding, Nigerian agriculture, despite its importance, encounters various challenges such as climate variability, pest and disease outbreaks, market volatility, and insufficient infrastructure, which subject farming households to diverse risks that jeopardize productivity and food security (Ononogbo et al., 2024). Agricultural risks in Nigeria significantly affect smallholder farmers. These risks present as production uncertainty, price volatility, financial instability, and resource limitations that may result in crop failure, income reduction, and heightened susceptibility to poverty. The impact is more pronounced in rain-fed agricultural systems when farmers have insufficient access to irrigation, superior seeds, and other productivity-enhancing technologies (Akpan & Akpan, 2024). Thus, comprehending the socioeconomic elements that affect farmers' adoption of risk management measures is essential for improving agricultural resilience and sustainable development. Socioeconomic factors, including educational attainment, household income, farm size, access to financing, extension services, and farmers' experience, significantly influence the ability of farming households to adopt preventative risk management measures.

Farmers with advanced knowledge and enhanced access to information are more inclined to implement superior farming practices and diversification strategies that mitigate susceptibility to agricultural shocks, Ikoyo-Eweto, Adedokun, Archibong, and Okwuokenye (2024). Similarly, access to financial resources and institutional assistance allows farmers to invest in risk-reduction technologies and manage production uncertainty more effectively (Nwaogwugwu, Olanrewaju & Barry 2024).

The intercropping system is extensively employed by smallholder farmers in Nigeria, including the maize-cassava intercropping prevalent in the derived savanna zones in the context of this study. It enhances land productivity (elevated land-equivalent ratios), stabilizes seasonal yields, diversifies harvest timing (short-term for maize; long-term for cassava), and bolsters dietary diversity. Its benefits also include reducing pests and diseases, and using resources more effectively in situations with variable rainfall **Abirami et al., 2025**. In Nigeria's north-central region, where Kwara State is located, intercropping is a conventional practice among farming communities. This strategy increases production and resilience among resource-poor farmers. However, despite the potential benefits, the extent of adoption and the specific socioeconomic factors that drive farmers' decisions to implement preventive risk management strategies within these intercropping systems remain inadequately understood.

Previous studies have researched on maize-cassava inter-cropping system notably among them were, growth and yield performance of cassava/maize inter-crop

under different plant population density of maize by Adeniyani, Aluko, Olanipekun, Olasoj, and Aduramigba-Modupe (2014); profitability of cassava/maize on Iwo and Egbeda soil series in Oyo State, Nigeria authored by Abegunde, Shaba, Alaga, Adebayo, and Abiola (2017); and Oparinde, Amos, Aturamu and Daramola (2018), who examined attitudes towards risk and risk combating strategies among maize and cassava farmers in Southwest, Nigeria. These researches addressed intercropping system of maize-cassava but overlook integrated socioeconomic drivers of preventive strategies. This study, therefore, examines the socioeconomic drivers of preventive risk management and resilience in maize-cassava intercropping systems in Kwara State, Nigeria, with a view to providing insights that can inform policies, further research and interventions aimed at strengthening agricultural resilience and food security. The specific objectives were to (i) describe the socioeconomic characteristics of maize-cassava small-scale farmers, (ii) identify the sources of production risks encountered by maize-cassava small-scale farmers, (iii) determine the preventive management strategies adopted by maize-cassava small-scale farmers and (iv) analyze the factors influencing preventive management strategies of maize-cassava small-scale farmers in the study area.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Study Area

The study was conducted in Kwara State, Nigeria. Kwara State is located in North Central Nigeria between Latitudes 7°45'N to 9°30'N and Longitudes 2°30'E to 6°25'E.

The mean annual rainfall ranges between 1000mm and 1500mm. Kwara State has sixteen (16) Local Government Areas. The State has a total population of 2,371,089 persons (National Population Commission, 2011) and an estimated population of 3,551,000 in 2022 based on data from National Population Commission and National Bureau of Statistics (City Population, 2022). The State has a total land area of 32,500 square Kilometers (Kwara State Ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resources (KWSMANR), 2010). The state shares local boundaries with Oyo, Ondo, Ekiti, Osun States to the South; Kebbi and Niger to the north; Kogi to the East and an international border with the Republic of Benin to the West (Kwara State Planning Commission (KWSPC), 2007) The average temperature ranges between 27° and 35°C with a mean annual rainfall of 1,000-1,500mm. It has two main seasons- wet and dry. The wet season is between early April and late October while the dry season is between November and late March. The natural vegetation cover consists of rainforest in the South and Guinea Savannah to the North. The climatic condition, soil type, topography and vegetation cover in the state support the cultivation of several crops of economic importance

like maize, cassava, vegetables, millet, rice, yam cowpea, sorghum etc. The State is also suitable for raising livestock (Oladimeji, 2018).

Sampling Techniques and Sampling Size

For this study, a multi-stage sampling technique was used. Firstly, Kwara State, was purposively selected due to the preponderance of maize-cassava farmers. In the second stage, six out of sixteen Local

Government Areas (LGAs) were randomly sampled. The LGAs are: Ilorin-West, Ilorin-East, Asa, Offa, Irepodun and Ifelodun respectively. This was followed by a random selection of two communities from each LGA. Thus, Wara and Egbejila were selected from Ilorin-West LGA; Oke-Oyi and Iponu were selected in Ilorin-East LGA; Eyekorin and Afon were selected in Asa LGA; Kamonu and Igbewere were selected in Offa LGA; Ajase-Ipo and Oro were selected in Irepodun LGA; while Omupo and Idofian were selected in Ifelodun LGA as the third stage. Finally, from a sample frame of 150 maize-cassava farmers, registered with Agricultural Development Programme (ADP), 110 were randomly selected as the sample size using Yamane's (1967) formula for the study and it is specified as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} = 110$$

Where:

n = Sample Size of Maize-Cassava Farmers (Units)

N = Population of Maize-Cassava Farmers (Units)

e = Level of Precision (5%)

Method of Data Collection

This study used primary sources for its data. Using interviews and a carefully designed questionnaire, the researcher and skilled enumerators collected the data.

Method of Data Analysis

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to achieve the objectives of this study. Descriptive statistics were used to achieve objective (i), describe the socioeconomic characteristics of maize-cassava small-scale farmers. To identify the sources of

production risks encountered by maize-cassava small-scale farmers and to determine the preventive management strategies adopted by maize-cassava small-scale farmers in the study area, Henry Garrett's ranking technique (HGRT) was utilized for the objectives (ii) and (iii). The HGRT ranges from 1-6 and 1-4 percent respectively, and the position of each rank was obtained using the proportionality factor given. It has the benefit of arranging these based on their importance compared to a simple frequency distribution.

Following Dhanavandan (2016), the formula is given thus:

$$\text{Percentage Score} = \frac{100(R_{ij} - 0.5)}{N_j}$$

Where:

R_{ij} = Rank given for the i th variable by the j th maize-cassava farmer

N_j = Number of variables ranked by the j th maize-cassava farmer

The multivariate probit (MVP) model was used to analyze the factors influencing preventive management strategies of maize-cassava small-scale farmers in the study area for the objective (iv). The multivariate probit model is used when you have multiple correlated binary dependent variables that may be jointly determined (Cappellari & Jenkins, 2003).

The model is specified as:

Assume M binary outcomes for individual i :

$$Y_{um}^* = X_i \beta_m + \epsilon_{um}, m=1,2,\dots,M$$

$Y_{um} = 1$ if $Y_{um}^* > 0$, 0 if otherwise.

Y_{um}^* = latent (unobserved) variable

X_i = vector of factors influencing preventive management strategies of maize-cassava scale farmers in the study area.

β_m = parameter vector

ϵ_{um} = error terms normal distribution with zero mean

$$Y_i = \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \beta_7 X_7 + \epsilon_i$$

Where,

Y_{i1} = Spraying of pesticide (yes = 1, otherwise = 0)

Y_{i2} = Resistant varieties (yes = 1, otherwise = 0)

Y_{i3} = Inter-cropping strategy (yes = 1, otherwise = 0)

Y_{i4} = Fertilizer application (yes = 1, otherwise = 0)

Where:

Y_i^* = Unobserved variable representing the utility of adopting strategy k .

X_i = a vector of observed characteristics determining the choice of preventive strategy.

X_1 = Age (years)

X_2 = Household size (numbers)

X_3 = Farming experience (years)

X_4 = Educational level (years)

X_5 = Farmers association (years)

X_6 = Extension visits (yes = 1, otherwise = 0)

X_7 = Off farm income (Naira)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socioeconomic Characteristics of Maize-Cassava Small-Scale Farmers in the Study Area

As presented in Table 1, the result shows the socioeconomic characteristics of maize-cassava farmers in the study area.

The result shows that the majority (86.36%) of the respondents were male, and female maize-cassava small-scale farmers (13.64%) between 41 and 50 years, with a mean age of approximately 49 years. This indicates that most of the farmers are in their economically productive age bracket. This is in line with Owwoeye (2020), who reported a similar active working age group. The marital status of respondents shows that (98.18%) of the farmers were

married, while (1.82%) were divorced and widowed. This result is consistent with the findings of Ibrahim, Oformata, Jirgi, and Adewumi (2019), who reported that the majority of maize-based farmers in Niger State were married. In smallholder farming, the size of the household and the availability of labor are strongly related. And in this study, the average household size was 9 persons, with the majority (74.55%) having 6-10 persons. The educational level of the respondents in the study area also showed that they had one form or another of formal education (39.09%), secondary (25.45%), and tertiary, which could increase the adoption rates of improved technologies. This conforms with the findings of Ibrahim et al. (2019), who reported that formal education

can enhance their farming skills by adopting innovations. The average farm size in the study area was 1.90 hectares, with (58.18%) having between 1.1 and 2.0 hectares, while (30.91%) had between 2.1

and 4.0 hectares. This result is in line with Girei, Saingbe, Ohen and Umar (2018), who stated that most maize farmers were small-scale farmers with an average farm size of 1-2 hectares.

Table 1: Socioeconomic Characteristics of Maize-Cassava Small-Scale Farmers in the Study Area

Variables	Maize-Cassava (n=110) Freq	%	Mean
Sex			
Male	95	86.36	
Female	15	13.64	
Total	110	100	
Age(years)			
1-30	1	0.91	
31-40	12	10.91	
41-50	56	50.91	49
51-60	35	31.82	
61-70	6	5.45	
Total	110	100	
Marital Status			
Married	108	98.18	
Divorced	1	0.91	
Widow	1	0.91	
Total	110	100	
Household Size (Number)			
1-5	7	6.36	
6-10	82	74.55	9 persons
11-15	17	15.45	
16-20	4	3.64	
Total	110	100	
Level of Education			
Primary Education	20	18.18	
Secondary Education	43	39.09	
Tertiary Education.	28	25.45	
Adult Education	2	1.82	
Quranic Education	6	5.45	
No Formal Education	11	10.00	
Total	110	100	
Farm Size (Hectares)			
0.1-1.0	12	10.91	
1.1-2.0	64	58.18	
2.1-4.0	34	30.91	1.90
Total	110	100	
Farming Experience			
1-20	57	51.82	
21-30	41	37.27	18.82

31-40	12	10.91	
Total	110	100	
Off-Farm Income			
1,000-200,000	102	92.73	58,336.364
200,001-400,000	5	4.55	
400,001-600,000	3	2.73	
Total	110	100	
Extension Contact			
1-5	102	92.73	2
6-10	8	7.27	
Total	110	100	

Source: Computed from field Data, 2025

Sources of Production Risk Encountered by Maize-Cassava Small-Scale Farmers

Table 2 represents sources of production risk encountered by the maize-cassava small-scale farmers using the Henry Garrett Ranking Technique. Maize pest and diseases, erratic rainfall pattern, flood, destruction by animals, destruction by herdsmen, and bush fire were identified, prioritized and ranked by the farmers in the study area.

Based on the ranks assigned by maize-cassava farmers, a technique was employed to calculate the percentage score, and the scale value was estimated by employing the Henry Garrett scale conversion Table. The percentage score for each rank 1-6 was estimated.

The percentage scores evaluated for all six ranks were converted appropriately into scale values using the Garrett scale conversion table. The estimated scale values for 1st to 6th ranks were: 77, 63, 54, 46, 37 and 23, respectively. The (Fx), i.e., score value, was appraised for each factor appropriately by multiplying the obtained number of respondents (F) by the respective calculated scale value (x). The total score was found by adding the score

values (Fx) of each rank for every factor. The Mean score was then estimated to know the appropriate order of occurrence given by maize-cassava farmers for the factors.

Based on the results, the highest position prioritized or encountered was pests and diseases, as indicated with the highest Garrett score of 7594, and an average score of 69.04, which ranked 1st in this category. This result corroborates the findings of Ayinde, Omotesho and Adewumi (2008) who noted that the major causes of farm loss were pest and disease outbreaks, erratic rainfall patterns, price fluctuation, changes in government policies and theft. Also, erratic rainfall pattern with Garrett score of 6925 and average score of 62.95 was ranked 2nd, this was followed by destruction by herdsmen with Garrett score of 6471 and average score of 58.83, which was ranked 3rd respectively.

The Garrett scores for sources of risk encountered by maize-cassava farmers, such as destruction by animals, bush fire, and flood was calculated at 5230, 3493, and 3296, with average scores of 47.54, 31.75, and 29.96 were ranked 4th, 5th, and 6th respectively.

Table 2: Sources of Production Risk Encountered by Maize-Based Small-Scale Farmers in the Study Area

Production Risk	Rank Given by Maize-Cassava Farmers						Total	Average	Rank
	1 st * 77	2 nd * 63	3 rd * 54	4 th * 46	5 th * 37	6 th * 23			
Pest and Diseases	57 (4389)	39 (2457)	13 (702)	1 (46)	0 (0)	0 (0)	7594	69.04	1 st
Erratic Rainfall Pattern	25 (1925)	50 (3150)	30 (1620)	5 (230)	0 (0)	0 (0)	6925	62.95	2 nd
Flood	0 (0)	1 (63)	3 (162)	5 (230)	37 (1369)	64 (1472)	3296	29.96	6 th
Destruction by Animals	0 (0)	4 (252)	24 (1296)	72 (3312)	10 (370)	0 (0)	5230	47.54	4 th
Destruction by Herdsmen	27 (2079)	16 (1008)	40 (2160)	25 (1150)	2 (74)	0 (0)	6471	58.83	3 rd
Bush Fire	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (54)	4 (184)	60 (2220)	45 (1035)	3493	31.75	5 th

Source: Computed from field Data, 2025

Note: Figure in parentheses are estimated using $Fx = \text{Product of frequency and scale value}$.

Preventive Strategies Adopted by Maize-Cassava Small-Scale Farmers in the Study Area

The preventive management strategies adopted by the maize-cassava farmers were presented in Table 3. The preventive management strategies adopted were analyzed using Henry Garrett's Ranking Technique. The preventive management strategies adopted include: use of resistant varieties, inter-cropping strategy, spraying of chemicals and fertilizer application.

The maize-cassava farmers assign the ranks, and a Henry Garrett technique was employed to calculate the percentage score, and the scale value was estimated by employing the Garrett scale conversion Table. The percentage score for each rank 1-4 was estimated.

The percentage scores evaluated for all eight ranks were converted appropriately into scale values using the Garrett scale conversion Table. The estimated scale values for 1st to 4th ranks were: 80, 67, 60 and 53, respectively. The (Fx), i.e. score value, was appraised for each factor appropriately by multiplying the obtained number of respondents (F) with the respective calculated scale value (x). The total score was found by adding the score values (Fx) of each rank for every factor. The mean score was then estimated to determine the appropriate order of occurrence given by maize-cassava farmers for the factors.

Based on Henry Garret's ranking technique, it has been shown that 'use of resistant varieties' had the highest Garret score of 6781 and an average score of 61.62 and was

ranked 1st. Similarly, 'inter-cropping strategy' with a Garrett score of 6418 and an average score of 58.35 was ranked 2nd. Also, 'spraying of chemicals' with a Garrett score of 6144 and an average score of 55.85 was ranked 3rd. 'fertilizer application' with a

Garrett score of 5805 and an average score of 52.77 was ranked 4th. This result agrees with Ndem and Osondu (2018), who reported that the maize-cassava farmers used pesticides/herbicides and fertilizer application, respectively.

Farmers in the Study Area

Preventive Strategy	Rank Given by Maize-Cassava Farmers				Total	Average	Rank
	1 st * 80	2 nd * 67	3 rd * 60	4 th * 53			
Spraying of Chemicals	31 (2480)	21 (1407)	14 (840)	10 (530)	6144	55.85	3 rd
Use of Resistant Varieties	17 (1360)	41 (2747)	25 (1500)	5 (265)	6781	61.65	1 st
Intercropping Strategy	23 (1840)	13 (871)	30 (1800)	15 (795)	6418	58.35	2 nd
Fertilizer Application	9 (720)	4 (268)	27 (1620)	40 (2120)	5805	52.77	4 th

Source: Computed from field Data, 2025

Note: Figure in parentheses are estimated using $Fx = \text{Product of frequency and scale value}$.

Factors Influencing Preventive Management Strategies of Maize-Cassava Small-Scale Farmers in the Study Area

Information about the factors influencing the preventive strategies adopted by maize-cassava small-scale farmers was recorded in Table 4. All rho coefficients are positive and statistically significant, indicating strong complementarities among the four preventive strategies. The rejection of the independence hypothesis (LR χ^2 (6) = 58.4165) confirms that adoption decisions are jointly determined rather than

independent. The result of the multivariate probit model was estimated jointly for the categorical dependent variables, which were spraying of chemicals, use of resistant varieties, inter-cropping strategy and fertilizer application. Farming experience, educational level and off-farm income were the variables significant at different significant levels.

Farming experience significantly and positively influenced the use of resistant varieties (p<0.01). This may indicate that experienced farmers are more likely to have accumulated knowledge about climate

variability and pest trends, making them more inclined to adopt improved seed technologies as a long-term resilience strategy. Conversely, farming experience negatively influenced intercropping ($p < 0.10$). This may suggest that highly experienced farmers may rely on conventional methods they perceive as reliable, thereby reducing diversification practices. The findings of this study agree with those of Lunduka, Kumbirai, Cosmos, and Pepukai (2019), who found a positive and significant relationship between farming experience and adoption of drought-tolerant maize varieties. Education positively and significantly influenced the adoption of resistant varieties ($p < 0.05$). Education enhances farmers' ability to access, process, and utilize information on improved technologies. Literate farmers may better understand extension recommendations and the long-term benefits of improved

varieties, strengthening adaptive capacity and resilience. This finding is consistent with recent studies (Oyetunde-Usman & Shee, 2023), which highlight education as a critical driver of innovation adoption. Furthermore, off-farm income significantly and positively influenced the spraying of chemicals ($p < 0.01$). This suggests that liquidity plays a crucial role in financing short-term risk mitigation measures. Chemical spraying requires cash outlay; thus, farmers with diversified income sources are better positioned to absorb risk and invest in preventive inputs. This finding reinforces the importance of income diversification in strengthening resilience. his result agrees with the finding of Omoluabi and Ibitoye (2024), who stated that farming households with additional income sources are more resilient and more likely to adopt chemical spraying and other preventive measures.

Table 4: Factors Influencing Preventive Management Strategies of MaizeCassava Small-Scale Farmers in the Study Area

Variables	Spraying of Chemicals		Use of Resistant Varieties		Intercropping Strategy		Fertilizer Application	
	Coef (SE)	z-value	Coef (SE)	z-value	Coef (SE)	z-value	Coef (SE)	z-value
Age (X1)	0.009 (0.181)	0.54	-0.018 (0.223)	-0.84	0.318 (0.019)	1.60	0.027 (0.204)	1.33
Household Size (X2)	-0.017 (0.504)	-0.35	-0.908 (0.598)	-1.52	-0.049 (0.555)	-0.88	-0.001 (0.471)	-0.03
Farming Experience (X3)	-0.036 (0.416)	-0.87	0.117 (0.437)	2.68***	-0.073 (0.384)	-1.90*	-0.012 (0.036)	-0.34
Educational Level (X4)	-0.007 (0.007)	-1.03	0.015 (0.007)	2.13**	-0.008 (0.007)	-0.10	0.002 (0.006)	0.46
Farmers Association (X5)	0.248 (0.286)	0.86	0.254 (0.288)	0.88	0.177 (0.267)	0.66	0.064 (0.254)	0.25
Extension Visits (X6)	-0.769 (0.474)	-1.62	0.045 (0.398)	0.11	-0.088 (0.369)	-0.24	-0.406 (0.370)	-1.10
Off-Farm Income (X7)	0.339 (0.111)	3.03***	0.115 (0.079)	1.46	0.013 (0.068)	1.47	0.065 (0.065)	1.01
Constant	0.310 (1.124)	0.28	0.647 (1.391)	0.47	-0.132 (1.146)	-0.12	-0.533 (1.150)	-0.46
Diagnostic statistics								

$\rho_{21} = 0.679^{***}$ (0.196)

$\rho_{31} = 0.800^{***}$ (0.159)

$\rho_{41} = 0.428^{***}$ (0.171)

$\rho_{32} = 0.590^{***}$ (0.128)

$\rho_{42} = 0.664^{***}$ (0.089)

$\rho_{43} = 0.546^{***}$ (0.122)

Number of Observations = 110

Log Pseudolikelihood = -198.09551

Wald $\chi^2(28) = 48.61$

Prob > $\chi^2 = 0.0092$

Likelihood Ratio Test of Independence of Equations:

$\chi^2(6) = 58.4165$

***is significant at 1% level, ** is significant at 5% level, and * is significant at 10% level of significance.

Source: Computed field data 2025

Conclusion

The findings reveal that farmers adopt multiple risk management strategies jointly rather than in isolation, confirming strong complementarities in climate risk responses. Farming experience, education, and non-farm income significantly enhance the likelihood of adopting improved practices, strengthening households' adaptive capacity. Conversely, limited resources and weak institutional support constrain effective risk mitigation. The results underscore that resilience is not merely about single technology adoption but about integrated strategy portfolios. Strengthening farmers' socioeconomic capacity is therefore central to sustainable agricultural risk management.

Recommendations

This study therefore recommends;

1. Policies should promote integrated adaptation packages rather than single interventions, given the strong complementarities among risk management strategies.
2. Investment in farmer education, training, and experiential learning platforms with the help of extension agents should be intensified to enhance informed and strategic risk responses.
3. Programs that strengthen income diversification opportunities (especially non-farm income) should be supported to improve farmers' financial resilience and adaptive capacity.

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